

Georeferencing and Classification of Urban Trees Using Aerial and Street-Level Images, and Machine Learning

Paulo Roberto Ferreira Maciel¹, Rodrigo Smarzarzo²

¹UFV, Rodovia BR 230 KM 7, Rio Paranaíba - MG, CEP 38810-000 Rio Paranaíba - MG – Brazil – paulo.r.macie1@ufv.br

²UFV, Rodovia BR 230 KM 7, Rio Paranaíba - MG, CEP 38810-000 – Rio Paranaíba - MG – Brazil - smarzarzo@ufv.br

Keywords: Georeferencing, Open-Source, deep Learning, Remote Sensing, Classification Algorithms, Image Segmentation.

Abstract

This article discusses using machine learning and remote sensing to identify and classify tree species. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) captured aerial images, while a GPS-based system ensured accurate georeferencing. Ground-level photos, taken by a 360° camera, provided a thorough view of the study area. A large dataset of aerial and ground images was created to train models like Random Forests, Support Vector Machines, and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), focusing on the classification of tree species. Challenges include intraclass variability (differences within the same species) and interclass similarity (similarities between species), complicating the classification process. Color balance issues in cameras can also introduce unwanted hues. By integrating aerial and ground images with advanced machine learning algorithms, classification accuracy is expected to improve. Studies using CNNs, such as U-net, have demonstrated up to 84% accuracy in vegetation classification with high-resolution images. U-net’s proven ability in image segmentation makes it a reliable tool for geospatial data analysis, and applying it here could significantly enhance the classification and mapping of tree species.

1.0 Introduction

In the urban context, the planning of green areas has become a priority to improve the quality of life in cities, offering benefits such as mitigating heat islands, improving air quality, and promoting the well-being of the population. The detection and identification of trees from aerial images have proven to be a promising tool for environmental monitoring, urban planning, and green area conservation (HEROLD et al., 2019; MA, M. et al., 2021). However, challenges such as the difficulty of classifying trees in densely populated areas, the presence of shadows cast by buildings, and adverse lighting conditions in certain seasons highlight the need for additional methods to improve the accuracy of the results.

This work aims to develop a system that integrates aerial and street-level images using computer vision and machine learning techniques. The central motivation is to incorporate information from street-level images to improve the classification of trees that could not be accurately identified solely by aerial images. By combining these different perspectives, the proposed system seeks to provide a more robust and efficient solution for tree species recognition and categorization, aiding in ecological studies, urban planning, and other applications related to the sustainable management of natural resources.

This study enables the efficient identification of areas lacking vegetation, allowing for more precise public policies aimed at sustainable urban planning. The importance of studies focused on tree detection and identification goes far beyond technical advancements. These studies are essential for a variety of fields, such as ecology, urban planning, and environmental monitoring, contributing significantly to the sustainable management of natural resources and the development of effective public policies. For example, the need to reduce uncertainties in land-use mapping is crucial for water resource management, agriculture, and forestry. A clear example is the European Commission’s invest-

ment of 170 million dollars in a tree-counting system, aimed at recording the number and condition of trees, providing a basis for managing financial aid to farmers. In areas with complex agronomic characteristics, approaches that can define individual trees are especially needed to ensure efficient and effective management of these areas (DALIAKOPOULOS et al., 2009).

In the urban context, the importance of urban forests cannot be underestimated. With the rapid advancement of urbanization, environmental challenges such as air pollution, loss of green spaces, and the urban heat island effect arise. Urban trees play a vital role in regulating temperature, improving air quality, and managing urban ecosystems. However, the effectiveness of these functions depends directly on the spatial distribution and variety of tree species. Therefore, accurate tree species classification is essential for the sustainable development of cities. Traditional classification techniques are labor-intensive and inefficient, leading to the need for more modern approaches, such as remote sensing with UAVs (drones). The integration of multiple data sources, such as high-resolution RGB images, LiDAR, and hyperspectral data, has shown a significant increase in classification accuracy, reaching 94.68% in recent studies (WU et al., 2024).

In addition to its importance for ecology and urban planning, accurate tree detection plays a crucial role in vegetation management in urban areas, especially near power lines. Preventive tree pruning is an efficient measure to reduce the risks of power supply interruptions, such as cable breaks, short circuits, and fires that can occur due to vegetation interference with urban power distribution lines. These interferences are one of the leading causes of power outages, resulting in significant financial losses for distribution companies due to lower quality indicators and the need for constant maintenance (BERGMANN et al., 2024). The use of technologies such as LiDAR and spherical images, combined with Deep Learning (DL) methods, can automate vegetation inspection, overcoming the limitations of aerial images

and reducing the time and cost of manual monitoring. A recent study in four Brazilian cities demonstrated that this innovative approach, implemented on a web platform and mobile app, achieved an accuracy of over 94% in identifying interferences, showcasing its potential for large-scale applications and contributing to the efficient maintenance of the power grid.

These advancements not only improve the management of urban and rural forests but also contribute to more conscious and efficient planning in cities seeking to mitigate the environmental impacts of uncontrolled urbanization. Thus, the study and application of remote sensing and computer vision technologies in the context of tree detection are fundamental for maintaining environmental health and ensuring the sustainable development of cities and rural areas.

The general objective of this project is to develop a tree detection and classification system from ground-level images that serves as an auxiliary module to improve the classification performed by models based on aerial images (satellite or drone) with the support of image processing and computer vision algorithms.

2.0 Related Work

To develop systems that detect and identify trees using aerial and ground-level images, it is essential to have a solid understanding of remote sensing (RS) technologies, image processing, and machine learning. In this section, we explore the key theoretical concepts and technological advancements that underpin this work. This includes the use of satellites and drones for RS, image correction and pre-processing techniques, object segmentation and classification in computer vision, as well as the specific challenges in tree detection across varied environments. We also review previous studies that applied these technologies for vegetation mapping and monitoring, providing a solid foundation for the implementation of the proposed system.

2.1 Remote Sensing and Satellite Images

Remote Sensing (RS) is a sophisticated technique that allows the collection of information about the Earth's surface without the need for direct contact. This is achieved by capturing solar radiation that strikes the Earth or through artificial electromagnetic radiation (FIGUEIREDO, 2005).

The sensors involved in this process can collect a diverse range of raw data, which includes, but is not limited to, visible light, infrared, and microwaves, among other frequencies. After collection, these data are transmitted via telemetry to ground stations.

At ground stations, the data undergo processing and storage through specialized systems. This allows the collected information to be effectively used for a variety of applications. The sensors function similarly to cameras, capturing electromagnetic waves and converting them into digital values or electronic pulses. This transformation is performed based on the intensity of the captured energy.

Optical sensors rely on sunlight, as they capture electromagnetic radiation reflected by the Earth's surface. For this reason, these sensors are called passive. They are excellent for detecting different types of objects due to their physical-chemical compositions, texture, and density (FIGUEIREDO, 2005). On the other hand, there are sensors that generate their own energy and operate in the microwave range. This characteristic allows them to function both day and night, and under any weather conditions. This is the main advantage of active sensors (FLORENZANO, 2007).

The ability of a sensor to discriminate objects based on their size is called spatial resolution. In current sensors, installed on orbital platforms (artificial satellites), this type of resolution ranges from 50 cm to 1 km. For example, a sensor with a spatial resolution of 10 m can detect objects larger than 100 m². Spectral resolution refers to a sensor's ability to distinguish objects based on its sensitivity to different parts of the electromagnetic spectrum. Sensors with narrower spectral bands are more likely to detect small variations in reflected energy. Additionally, a sensor with more bands or channels has superior spectral resolution, as each additional band offers greater spectral discrimination capability.

The temporal resolution of a sensor refers to how frequently it captures images of a particular area. For example, the TM-Landsat-5 sensor has a temporal resolution of 16 days, meaning it captures images of the same area every 16 days. This is less frequent than the sensor aboard the meteorological satellite Goes, which captures images of the same side of the Earth every half hour. Thus, the temporal resolution of the Goes sensor is higher than that of the TM-Landsat-5 (FLORENZANO, 2007).

Satellite images are incredible tools that help in many fields. They monitor vegetation, aiding in forest protection and the development of effective public policies. Additionally, they identify water-scarce areas, monitor water quality, and help prevent desertification. In agriculture, they track crop growth, identify irrigation problems, and help predict yield, making agricultural management more efficient and sustainable. These images are essential for assessing environmental impact, analyzing changes in land cover over time, and monitoring human activities. They are also vital for resource management, such as in forestry and mining operations (GEOINOVA, 2024; WU et al., 2024).

2.2 Drone Imaging Technologies

A drone is an aircraft operated without a human pilot on board, autonomously controlled by computers or remotely by a ground operator (PHANG et al., 2023). Its ability to fly and maneuver is made possible by rotors or propellers, allowing for various maneuvers. Equipped with sensors, cameras, and other payloads, drones have numerous functionalities, adapting to the intended use (MA, J. et al., 2024).

There are several types of cameras used in drones, selected according to the project's objectives and available resources. The RGB camera operates within the visible spectrum. It is capable of capturing images in the range of light visible to the human eye, similar to conventional cameras found in devices like smartphones. This camera enables the collection of quantitative terrain data, allowing for detailed analyses and the generation of topographic maps. These analyses can include information such as geographic coordinates, distances, areas, perimeters, and other relevant aspects.

A multispectral camera is a sophisticated tool that acquires images in multiple bands of the electromagnetic spectrum, which can extend beyond the visible light range to near-infrared (NIR). After capturing, the images are analyzed, enabling precise identification of areas where plants are under stress, as well as the detection of nutritional deficiencies and other problems that may affect plant health. Additionally, multispectral cameras have a remarkable ability to detect the presence of weeds and pests, providing a comprehensive view of the ecosystem's health (DRO-NENG, 2024).

Thermal cameras detect the temperature of objects and people through the infrared radiation they emit. Using a hybrid lens, they combine common thermal information to generate visible

images. They are employed in security, fire detection, and temperature measurement, and can quickly identify multiple people, useful in scenarios like the COVID-19 pandemic (AEON2023, 2024).

Drones equipped with thermal cameras are a valuable tool in agriculture and vegetation research. They can even identify the morphological and anatomical characteristics of plants, thus offering more accurate experimental data. They also detect water stress, diseases, and pests before they become visible, allowing farmers to take preventive actions (CNPTIA, 2024).

Before the popularization of small-scale UAVs, near-ground remote sensing was primarily carried out by manned aircraft equipped with multispectral or electro-optical (EO) sensors. These missions, like one conducted in 1998 using a Cessna U206 to monitor pests and stress in wheat crops, provided high resolution but were costly and time-consuming operations (PHANG et al., 2023). With the advancement of UAVs (drones), a more affordable and agile alternative emerged, allowing for the capture of high-resolution images more frequently.

However, while drones offer superior spatial resolution, particularly for precision agriculture and local monitoring, satellite images still play an important role. Satellite images have the advantage of covering large geographical areas at once, which is ideal for large-scale monitoring. However, they have limitations in terms of spatial resolution compared to drones. Satellites, while accessible for certain types of monitoring, may not provide the level of detail needed for applications that require more refined analysis, such as the precise identification of small field variations.

Drones have played an important role in improving the image resolution used in precision agriculture. Due to their lower flight altitude and closer proximity to the ground compared to manned aircraft, drones capture more details of crops, thus offering better resolution for assessing crop and soil conditions. This makes them highly useful tools for optimizing environmental management and providing informed decision support (PHANG et al., 2023).

While drones offer significantly improved resolution compared to manned aircraft, allowing for more precise capture of crop and soil details, using this technology in complex environments, such as forested or urban areas, presents specific challenges. The quality and resolution of the captured images are not always sufficient to overcome the difficulties associated with detecting trees in various stages of growth or in scenarios with shadows and obstructions.

The research conducted by Everaldo M. Lima Neto and Biondi (2012) highlighted three significant challenges in detecting trees using drones. The variation in canopy size and tree height, the shadow cast by buildings over trees, and the influence of the time of year are factors that complicate the use of this technology. Canopy variation is an issue because a newly planted tree does not have a well-defined canopy, making detection difficult. Additionally, buildings and mountains can interfere with the shadow removal process, overlapping some trees that end up being mistakenly eliminated.

2.3 Image Processing and Computer Vision

In the context of satellite images, the vast volume of data and the complexity of calculations indeed demand significant computational resources. Digital processing has become a major investment area due to high demand, and this is particularly true for satellite images.

According to recent research, greater computational resources are essential to manage the volume and complexity of satellite data processing. For example, one study highlights the role of advanced digital processing techniques, such as adaptive deep learning, in monitoring the conditions of the gearbox of wind turbines using satellite data. This requires high computational power to handle large datasets and complex algorithms (TAO et al., 2024).

According to Marques Filho and Hugo Vieira Neto, 1999, filtering methods can be classified into two categories: spatial filtering and frequency domain filtering. Spatial filtering operates directly on the pixel matrix, which is the representation of the digitized image itself. The image processing function, normally applied to a 3 x 3 region, can be expressed as:

$$g(x,y) = T[f(x,y)] \quad (1)$$

such that: $(g(x,y))$ is the result of processing the image $(f(x,y))$ and (T) is an operator.

For cases where the neighborhood is 1 x 1, the operator (T) becomes a transformation function that can be expressed by:

$$s = T(r) \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, filtering that operates in the frequency domain is based on methods that utilize the Fourier transform. Let $g(x,y)$ be the image formed by the convolution (denoted by the symbol $*$) of the image $f(x,y)$ with a linear operator $h(x,y)$, that is, $g(x,y) = f(x,y) * h(x,y)$.

Then, by the convolution theorem, it is possible to establish the following relationship:

$$G(u,v) = F(u,v)H(u,v),$$

such that G , F , and H are the Fourier transforms of g , f , and h , in that order. There are different types of filters, such as low-pass, high-pass, and band-pass. The resulting image is obtained by applying the inverse of the Fourier transform. During image capture, distortions and variations in the recorded radiance may occur due to atmospheric factors, lighting, geometric shape, and even the characteristics of the sensor itself (FIGUEIREDO, 2005).

Radiometric correction in digital aerial images aims to make the histograms of images similar, especially when there is overlap between them. This facilitates subsequent processes such as homologous point matching and mosaic formation.

To achieve this, several techniques will be developed to minimize the effects resulting from the interaction of electromagnetic radiation with particles present in the atmosphere. These techniques can be divided into physical, empirical, and hybrid methods.

Physical methods, or radiative transfer or absolute methods, use physical estimates of atmospheric parameters to correct images by simulating the propagation of electromagnetic radiation through the atmosphere, such as the Second Simulation of the Satellite Signal in the Solar Spectrum (6S).

Empirical methods are simpler and less precise as they are based on rough estimates of atmospheric parameters. The advantage of this method is the lack of need for acquiring atmospheric parameters at the time of image acquisition, such as Dark Object Subtraction (DOS).

The hybrid method combines simple versions of the physical model with statistical data from the scene. Some of these methods also use in situ reflectance measurements to remove residual errors that persisted after correction (LANGHI; TOMMASELLI, 2008).

After the acquisition, processing, and correction of the images, the segmentation and classification of the objects of interest can then be carried out. Patrícia da Silva, Santos Filho, and Sérgio Francisco da Silva (2019) present some approaches for image segmentation for tree detection, such as template matching, region growing segmentation, and peak detection. The template matching technique creates several models that characterize a tree, considering radiometric and geometric properties. After the templates are created, the process of finding the best matches is performed, meaning the region that is most likely to represent a tree.

2.4 Challenges in Tree Detection and Identification

The detection and identification of trees face additional challenges, as pointed out by research. The use of filters for shadow detection, as in the work of DOS SANTOS, DALMOLIN, and BASSO (2006), can eliminate tree crowns that are of similar heights. Furthermore, some species of trees, known as deciduous trees, lose their leaves during the dry and cold periods of the year. Detecting these trees in autumn becomes even more challenging due to the lack of foliage, making it difficult to form detection polygons.

Studies conducted by Lombardi et al. (2022) highlight that the morphology of trees exhibits significant diversity among different species. This variation is especially noticeable in aspects such as crown structure, leaf shape, and growth patterns.

An illustrative example of this diversity can be observed in pine species. Research that utilized images obtained from drones equipped with LiDAR and RGB cameras revealed considerable intraspecific variation in crown architecture and biomass among these pine species. This variation can be attributed to genetic differences between species, as well as adaptations developed in response to local climatic conditions.

As demonstrated by Everaldo M Lima Neto and Biondi (2012), the presence of shadows significantly interferes with the detection and identification of trees. Shadows can originate from buildings, especially in the case of urban vegetation, or even from the trees themselves, which cast shadows on themselves. The situation becomes even more complicated when the color of the crown is similar to the shadow projected on the ground, making it difficult to precisely delineate the crown. Additionally, there are cases where trees exhibit multiple distinct regions in their crowns. The terrain and the quality of the sensors have also been noted as complicating factors.

As highlighted by Arantes et al. (2020), the presence of tree crowns spaced crowns facilitate the detection and individualization of trees, as the resulting mosaics exhibit enhanced definition. This aerial remote sensing technique proves particularly useful in forested areas, where ground-level access is challenging. In contrast, images captured at ground level play a crucial role in identifying streets that lack tree cover and roads with varying levels of tree cover or deforestation over time (BAHETY et al., 2022).

2.5 Tools and Technologies Used

This section presents the main tools and technologies used for the acquisition, processing, and analysis of data in the tree detection and classification project.

2.5.1 Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

UAVs will be essential for capturing high-resolution images of the study areas. Equipped with a high-resolution camera, drones allow for the collection of aerial data with georeferenced precision, providing a detailed view of tree crowns. The choice of drone was based on its ability to fly at suitable altitudes for capturing images with high spatial resolution, obtaining information detailed information about complex urban areas, which is essential for the detection of individual trees (WU et al., 2024).

2.5.2 Image Processing Software

For the processing and analysis of the captured images, we will use Quantum GIS (QGIS), a software widely used for photogrammetry and 3D reconstruction. This software allows for the creation of orthomosaics and the generation of digital elevation models (DEM), which are essential for analyzing topography and tree crowns. ArcGIS may also be used for image processing and manipulation, providing support for geoprocessing and integration with other geospatial data.

2.5.3 Computer Vision and Machine Learning Algorithms

We will employ computer vision and machine learning for tree detection and classification. Convolutional neural networks will be trained to segment tree crowns and detect the tree species. TensorFlow and PyTorch are the main frameworks we will use to implement deep learning models.

2.5.4 GNSS

GNSS will be used to georeference the images and to collect the exact location of the detected trees. This technology allows for the combination of image information with highly accurate geospatial data, which is practical for mapping and analyzing the relevant spaces.

2.5.5 OpenStreetMap

For tree detection and classification, computer vision algorithms such as U-Net will be used. CNNs will be trained to segment the crowns in the images and identify different tree species. TensorFlow and PyTorch will be the main libraries used in the development of the deep learning models.

2.5.6 Practical Applications

The practical applications of SR and computer vision have shown great relevance in various areas of agriculture and environmental management. For example, plant counting is crucial for agricultural and forestry management, providing accurate data on irrigation, fertilization, productivity, and carbon stock, as well as allowing for the monitoring of plant mortality associated with diseases and environmental factors (DALIAKOPOULOS et al., 2009).

Advances in satellite image quality and the use of UAVs has facilitated tree counting, replacing time-consuming and error-prone field surveys (SILVA, P. da; SANTOS FILHO; SILVA, S. F. da, 2019). Similarly, in vine cultivation, SR has been used for disease mapping, vigor assessment, and canopy density estimation, with UAVs providing high spatial and temporal resolution data at lower costs (PÁDUA et al., 2020). Additionally, the use of mobile platforms for urban inventory, as in the city of Monte

Carmelo - MG, has shown efficiency in the geolocation and management of urban trees, allowing for the precise georeferencing of thousands of trees in a reduced time frame (BARBOSA et al., 2018).

Finally, the automation of species identification, driven by computer vision and mobile devices, has revolutionized botany, making biodiversity knowledge more accessible to non-experts, with methods achieving high accuracy in plant species classification (WÄLDCHEN; MÁDER, 2018).

3.0 Methods

This chapter details the methodologies used for data collection, both aerial and ground-based, essential for tree classification.

3.1 Data Collection

The data collection was divided into two complementary approaches: aerial data collection using UAVs and ground-based data collection using vehicles equipped with cameras.

3.1.1 Aerial Data Collection

Data collection will be carried out using drones equipped with high-definition RGB cameras. The images will be captured during different seasons to assess the impact of seasonality on tree detection, considering variations in canopy density and foliage. Images of urban areas, where the presence of obstacles such as buildings may interfere with image quality, will also be considered. The city was divided into specific zones to optimize data collection, using pre-planned routes to ensure complete coverage of the area of interest.

3.1.2 Ground Data Collection

Ground data collection will be conducted using a portable capture system, which will be used on foot or by bicycle. This system will include a spherical camera and a GNSS module to record georeferenced images and videos of trees from ground level. Operators will travel through urban and peri-urban areas of Rio Paranaíba. The captured images, with date and time stamps, will be synchronized to ensure the correct spatial identification of trees, complementing the information captured by aerial data collection.

3.1.3 Image Processing

The collected images will be pre-processed to remove noise and atmospheric distortions using radiometric correction methods, followed by three main processing steps: spatial filtering with convolution operators to smooth and detect edges, frequency-domain filtering using Fourier Transform to remove periodic distortions, and binarization for segmenting objects of interest, complemented by morphological operations to refine the detected shapes.

Figure 1: zoning of Rio Paranaíba

4.0 Segmentation and Classification

The collected images will be pre-processed to remove noise and atmospheric distortions using radiometric correction methods, followed by three main processing steps: (1) spatial filtering, (2) frequency-domain filtering, and (3) binarization and morphological operations for segmentation and refinement of the objects of interest.

4.1 Spatial Filtering

Spatial filtering will be performed by applying convolution operators over 3x3 regions of the image, aiming to smooth and detect important edges in the images. This approach can mitigate unwanted noise, allowing for precise identification of the contours of trees, especially their canopies.

4.1.1 Frequency-Domain Filtering

To enhance the definition of objects, the Fourier Transform will be applied, enabling the removal of periodic distortions and low-frequency artifacts. This method results in a clearer definition of the relevant structures of trees, such as the canopies and trunks, improving the contrast and distinction of elements present in the images.

4.1.2 Binarization and Morphological Operations

After filtering, the images will undergo binarization techniques, such as the Otsu method, for segmentation of the objects of interest. This binarization transforms the images into a binary format (black and white) where the trees will be highlighted against the background. Segmentation can be refined with morphological operations, such as dilation and erosion, which reduce smaller noise and connect disjoint components, improving the continuity of the detected shapes.

4.2 Tools and Software

The main software and tools are discussed in this part of the report, which will be adopted for the data preprocessing phase, in order to prepare the collected images and information so that they can be effectively processed by the detection and classification techniques. These tools are of great importance for cleaning and processing raw images, correcting and merging geospatial data.

4.2.1 TensorFlow

TensorFlow is one of the leading deep learning libraries widely used in the development and training of artificial neural networks. In preprocessing, this library will be used to prepare the training data, which includes normalizing images, resizing, and contrast adjustments, as well as handling large image datasets. It also provides support for creating efficient data pipelines, enabling batch loading and parallel processing of data.

4.2.2 OpenCV

OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision Library) is a widely used computer vision library for image processing. In the context of preprocessing, OpenCV will be essential for applying various techniques, such as

1. **Distortion Correction:** Correcting geometric distortions in images captured by drones.
2. **Color Adjustments:** Performing adjustments for brightness, contrast, and color balancing, making the data more uniform.
3. **Filtering and Smoothing:** Applying filters to remove unwanted noise from images.
4. **Initial Segmentation:** Performing preliminary segmentations, such as highlighting areas of interest (tree canopies) in the images to facilitate later processing

4.2.3 QGIS

QGIS (Quantum GIS) is an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) software used for visualization, editing, and analysis of geospatial data. In preprocessing, QGIS will play a fundamental role in:

1. **Georeferencing:** Adjusting and aligning the images captured by drones with precise spatial coordinates, ensuring that the data is correctly positioned in geographic space.
2. **Data Integration:** Combining images and layers of geospatial data, such as Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), topographic maps, and land use layers, providing a richer context for analysis.
3. **Atmospheric Correction:** Applying atmospheric corrections to satellite images, removing interferences caused by the atmosphere and ensuring that the data is ready for analysis.
4. **QGIS will be essential for organizing and processing geospatial data, preparing it for analysis in the next stages of the project.**

QGIS will be essential for organizing and processing geospatial data, preparing it for analysis in the next stages of the project.

4.2.4 Keras

Keras is a powerful high-level library for building and training neural networks in Python, integrated with TensorFlow. With an intuitive interface, Keras simplifies the development of complex deep learning models, making it an ideal choice for projects involving computer vision, such as tree detection and classification. The main advantage of Keras is its ability to enable the efficient construction of convolutional neural network (CNN) models, allowing researchers and developers to focus on model design without worrying about low-level implementation details.

4.2.5 OpenStreetMap

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is a collaborative platform that provides an open-source geospatial database, powered by voluntary contributions from mappers around the world. Through APIs like the Overpass API, it is possible to extract detailed information about trees mapped at street level. These community-generated data allow for the precise identification of the location of individual trees or groups of trees in urban areas. The integration of this information with computer vision algorithms and images captured by drones can significantly enhance tree classification, providing a more accurate view of urban vegetation.

Figure 2: model stages

4.3 Evaluation of Results

The evaluation of the results will be conducted based on a series of quantitative and qualitative metrics, focusing on the accuracy, consistency, and efficiency of the data generated by the tree detection model. The main aspects to be considered in the evaluation include:

Accuracy in Tree Detection: The accuracy of the model will be assessed by comparing the automatically detected trees with a reference dataset (ground truth). The accuracy metric will be obtained by comparing the correct predictions (true positives) with the errors (false positives and false negatives).

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives (TP)}}{\text{True Positive (TP) + False Positive (FP)}} \quad (3)$$

False Positive and False Negative Rates: The rates of false positives (objects incorrectly identified as trees) and false negatives (trees present in the images but not detected by the models)

will be calculated. These rates will help assess the balance between the sensitivity and specificity of the models. Subsequently, a confusion matrix will be generated to evaluate the overall performance of the model, allowing for a detailed analysis of correct and incorrect classifications, as well as providing insights into the model's behavior regarding precision and recall.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives (TP)}}{\text{True Positives (TP)} + \text{False Negatives (FN)}} \quad (4)$$

Computational Efficiency: The model's performance will be analyzed in terms of processing time and resource consumption. Efficiency will be an important criterion, especially for large-scale applications, where fast and optimized processing is essential.

Comparison with Other Data Sources: The results obtained will be compared with data obtained from other means, such as aerial images from drones and geospatial data. The ability to integrate different data sources will be assessed, ensuring that the model is robust and capable of combining information from different perspectives (aerial and terrestrial).

Model Robustness in Different Scenarios: The model's effectiveness will be evaluated in various types of environments, including urban and rural areas. Aspects such as tree density, variations in lighting conditions, and the complexity of the scene (presence of visual obstacles, such as buildings or vehicles) will be considered.

5.0 Results

The main focus of this project is to design an integrated system that can combine street-level tree images obtained from OpenStreetMap with aerial tree images captured by drones into a single training dataset, to support the classification of tree species in both urban and rural environments. Thus, the following outcomes are anticipated:

Enhanced Tree Classification: By merging ground-level images and aerial images captured by drones, the trained model should be more capable of classifying and identifying tree species. Street-level photos can provide qualitative and highly descriptive information regarding species, shape, color, and distinctive characteristics of leaves, bark, and crowns, complementing aerial photos.

Improved Species Identification Accuracy: The availability of both terrestrial and aerial images will greatly increase the model's accuracy in identifying species, especially in areas with dense vegetation and urban complexity. The system will be able to identify specific species with similar characteristics that cannot be discerned from aerial images alone.

Development of a Universal Tool for Various Applications: The tool to be developed will have multiple practical applications in ecology, urban planning, environmental monitoring, and natural resource management. It will provide precise information about biodiversity, assist in tree planning and management, and facilitate monitoring of environmental changes.

Robustness in Detection Across Diverse Environments: The model will be robust in urban, rural, and natural environments. The combination of aerial and terrestrial data will allow analyses in situations where purely aerial data would be limited, such as areas with dense vegetation or visual obstructions.

Improvement in Environmental Monitoring and Natural Resource Management: The solution will enable monitoring of tree

health, detection of ecosystem damage, and support for the management of urban and rural forests, providing automated, real-time insights into the state of trees.

Efficiency in Data Collection and Processing: The system will automate much of the data collection, annotation, and analysis process, resulting in greater efficiency and scalability for large projects with real-time monitoring.

References

- AEON2023. Câmeras térmicas: o que são, sua importância e como funcionam. 2024. Accessed: 2024-05-07. Disponível em: <https://aeon.com.br/cameras-termicas-o-que-e-sao-sua-importancia-e-como-funcionam/>.
- ANDRADE, B. G. d. et al. Visão computacional para identificação de espécies lenhosas em campo. Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro, 2020.
- ARANTES, B. H. T. et al. Efficiency analysis of the use of model matching algorithm for plant counting. *Research, Society and Development*, v. 9, n. 7, e668974576, mai. 2020. DOI: 10.33448/rsd-v9i7.4576. Disponível em: <https://rsdjournal.org/index.php/rsd/article/view/4576>.
- BAHETY, A. et al. Automatic Quantification and Visualization of Street Trees. *CoRR*, abs/2201.06569, 2022. arXiv: 2201.06569. Disponível em: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.06569>.
- BARBOSA, R. L. et al. Quantificação e georreferenciamento semiautomático de árvores urbanas. *REVSBAU, Curitiba-PR*, v13, n. 4, p. 41–53, 2018. BERGMANN, M. A. et al. An approach based on LiDAR and spherical images for automated vegetation inspection in urban power distribution lines. *IEEE Access*, IEEE, 2024.
- CNPTIA, E. Documento técnico sobre práticas agrícolas. 2024. Accessed: 2024-05-07. Disponível em: <https://ainfo.cnptia.embrapa.br/digital/bitstream/item/213109/1/CNPAF-2019-jt-p17.pdf>.
- DALIAKOPOULOS, I. N. et al. Tree crown detection on multispectral VHR satellite imagery. *Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing, American Society for Photogrammetry e Remote Sensing*, v. 75, n. 10, p. 1201–1211, 2009.
- DOS SANTOS, D. R.; DALMOLIN, Q.; BASSO, M. A. Detecção automática de sombras em imagens de alta resolução. *Boletim de Ciências Geodésicas, Universidade Federal do Paraná*, v. 12, n. 1, p. 87–99, 2006.
- DRONENG. Tipos de câmeras para drones e as imagens geradas. 2024. <https://blog.droneng.com.br/tipos-de-cameras-para-drones/>. Accessed: 2024-05-07. Disponível em: <https://blog.droneng.com.br/tipos-de-cameras-para-drones/>.
- FIGUEIREDO, D. Conceitos básicos de sensoriamento remoto. São Paulo, 2005.
- FLORENZANO, T. G. Iniciação em sensoriamento remoto. Oficina de textos, 2007. REFERÊNCIAS 35
- GOINOVA. Monitoramento por imagem de satélite: uma ferramenta essencial para a gestão de recursos naturais. 2024. <https://goinova.com.br/monitoramento-p-or>

- imagem-de-satelite-uma-ferramenta-essencial-para-a-gestao-de-recursos-naturais/. Accessed: 2024-05-07. Disponível em: <https://geoinova.com.br/monitoramento-por-imag-em-de-satelite-uma-ferramenta-essencial-para-a-gestao-de-recursos-naturais/>.
- HEROLD, M. et al. The role and need for space-based forest biomass-related measurements in environmental management and policy. *Surveys in Geophysics*, Springer, v. 40, p. 757–778, 2019.
- LANGHI, P.; TOMMASELLI, A. M. G. Correção radiométrica de imagens aéreas digitais por meio de ajuste polinomial. *Simpósio Brasileiro de Ciências Geodésicas e Tecnologias da Geoinformação*, UFPE, 2008.
- LOMBARDI, E. et al. UAV-LiDAR and RGB Imagery Reveal Large Intraspecific Variation in Tree-Level Morphometric Traits across Different Pine Species Evaluated in Common Gardens. *Remote Sensing*, v. 14, n. 22, 2022. ISSN 2072-4292. DOI: 10.3390/rs14225904. Disponível em: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/14/22/5904>.
- MA, J. et al. Research on Vision-Based Servoing and Trajectory Prediction Strategy for Capturing Illegal Drones. *Drones*, v. 8, n. 4, 2024. ISSN 2504-446X. DOI: 10.3390/drones8040127. Disponível em: <https://www.mdpi.com/2504-446X/8/4/127>.
- MA, M. et al. Tree Species Classification Based on Sentinel-2 Imagery and Random Forest Classifier in the Eastern Regions of the Qilian Mountains. *Forests*, v. 12, n. 12, 2021. ISSN 1999-4907. DOI: 10.3390/f12121736. Disponível em: <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-4907/12/12/1736>.
- MARQUES FILHO, O.; NETO, H. V. *Processamento digital de imagens*. Brasport, 1999.
- NETO, E. M. L.; BIONDI, D. Detecção de árvores de ruas da cidade de Curitiba, PR, utilizando fotografias aéreas. *Revista Brasileira de Ciências Agrárias*, Universidade Federal Rural de Pernambuco, v. 7, n. 4, p. 641–647, 2012.
- PÁDUA, L. et al. Individual grapevine analysis in a multi-temporal context using UAV-based multi-sensor imagery. *Remote Sensing*, MDPI, v. 12, n. 1, p. 139, 2020.
- PHANG, S. K. et al. From Satellite to UAV-Based Remote Sensing: A Review on Precision Agriculture. *IEEE Access*, v. 11, p. 127057–127076, nov. 2023. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3330886.
- SÁ, C. d. S. et al. Detecção semiautomática de árvores em pomar de mangueira irrigada a partir de imagens obtidas por drone. *Irriga*, v. 26, n. 3, p. 507-524, 2021., 2021.
- SILVA, P. da; SANTOS FILHO, T. A. dos; SILVA, S. F. da. Metodologias de visão computacional para contagem de plantas por meio de imagens de satélite. In: *ANAIS da VII Escola Regional de Informática de Goiás*. Goiânia: SBC, 2019. P. 143–154. Disponível em: <https://sol.sbc.org.br/index.php/erigo/article/view/9092>. REFERÊNCIAS 36
- SILVA, P. D. da; SANTOS FILHO, T. A. dos; SILVA, S. F. da. Metodologias de visão computacional para contagem de plantas por meio de imagens de satélite. In: *SBC. ANAIS da VII Escola Regional de Informática de Goiás*. 2019. P. 143–154.
- TAO, H. et al. An Online Digital Imaging Excitation Sensor for Wind Turbine Gearbox Wear Condition Monitoring Based on Adaptive Deep Learning Method. *Sensors*, v. 24, n. 8, 2024. ISSN 1424-8220. DOI: 10.3390/s24082481. Disponível em: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/24/8/2481>.
- WÄLDCHEN, J.; MÄDER, P. Plant species identification using computer vision techniques: A systematic literature review. *Archives of computational methods in engineering*, Springer, v. 25, p. 507–543, 2018.
- WU, J. et al. Fine Classification of Urban Tree Species Based on UAV-Based RGB Imagery and LiDAR Data. *Forests*, MDPI, v. 15, n. 2, p. 390, 2024.